

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**COMPULSIVE BUYING DUE TO STRESS LEADING TO SHOPPING
ADDICTION AMONG WORKING WOMEN****Rafaina Shah¹, Mohammed Zakaria², Aatir H. Rajput³,
Muhammad Muneeb⁴, Abid Ali⁵ and Anam Shaikh⁶.**Lecturer – Dept. of Community Medicine & Public Health, Indus Medical College, T.M.K¹Asst Prof – Dept. of Community Medicine, Sir Syed College of Medical Sciences, Karachi¹M.D Scholar – Dept. of Psychiatry, Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences³Coordinator – Department of Medical Education, Indus Medical College, T.M.K⁶LUMHS Research Forum^{5 & 6}**Abstract**

Background: Compulsive buying is a chronic behavior of repetitive purchasing that occurs as a result of negative feelings and owing to the constantly high levels of negative stimuli such as work-stress among working women, it is becoming a way of life.

Objective: To assess the prevalence of compulsive buying and eventual shopping addiction among working women and study its association with stress.

Methodology: This descriptive analysis was carried out from January 2017 to June 2017 upon a sample of 384 female employees (consenting faculty members of 3 major universities of Jamshoro, ranked BPS-18 and above) of Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences, University of Sindh and Mehran University of Engineering and Technology (MUET), chosen via non-probability, purposive sampling. Data was obtained via a self-structured, self-administered questionnaire and the Perceived Stress Scale after taking written informed consent. The data obtained was analyzed using SPSS v. 19.0 and Microsoft Excel.

Results: The mean age of the sample of 384 females, stood at 42 (± 13 SD). 81.25% of the respondents were married, while the remaining 18.75% were un-married. 78.64% of the respondents hailed from an urban setting and the rest of 21.36 respondents belonged to rural areas. The respondents (BPS-18 and above) were designated either as lecturers (50%), assistant professors (26.5%), associate professors (14.6%) and professors (8.9%). The stress levels among the respondents were classified as low (26.56%), moderate (52.6%) and high (20.84%). 33.25% of the respondents were admittedly addicted to shopping, 48% of the respondents admitted to indulging in stress induced compulsive buying while the 18.75% of the respondents did not indulge in stress induced compulsive buying.

Conclusion: Stress induced compulsive shopping among working women is common, resulting in most of the women developing an addiction towards shopping. The temporary relief from stress obtained from shopping is thus not an innocent pleasure but a sign of an impending trouble, thus it needs to be avoided and more healthy stress relief habits should be promoted.

Keywords: Compulsive Buying, Stress, Shopping Addiction, Oniomania, Working Women, Public Health

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Please cite this article in press Muhammad Muneeb et al., *Compulsive Buying Due To Stress Leading to Shopping Addiction among Working Women.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(12).

INTRODUCTION:

Since the emergence of mankind, a spirit to get more has been experienced. In ancient times, humans satisfied this need through barter trade, which later with the advancement of human rationality changed into commodity money and at the present fiat money. Fiat money is easy to carry, does not carry the psychological weight of a barter and thus is spent much easily. It is often believed that the advent of fiat money coincides closely with the appearance and identification of oniomania, which means buying mania. [1] A fresher term is nowadays used to describe this mania, i.e. compulsive buying. [2]

Chronic behavior of repetitive purchasing that occurs as a result of negative feelings or events is compulsive buying. [3] Research on compulsive buying dates back to the last century when it was identified by Bleuler and Kraepelin, [4] by its former name (oniomania) and regarded as, an addiction. Since then, psychologists have defined compulsive buying as a tantalizing longing to buy, followed by a feeling of relief after making the purchase.

Buying or making purchase is a regular routine task for most people, however, compulsive buyers face an inability to control their buying behavior and they do not have control over themselves. Compulsive buyers do not merely buy or purchase for the utility of the product/service but they also find satisfaction in the purchasing process. Thus they have a tendency to make constant purchases without considering the utility of the product. Compulsive buyers have little or no control over their impulse. [5]

In the American general population there is a 5.8% lifetime prevalence of Compulsive buying disorder. Other prevalence estimates range 1-10% of adults in western developed countries, including the United Kingdom. Community based and clinical surveys shows that 80% to 95% of people with compulsive buying disorder are females. [6] Being female, experiencing symptoms of psychological distress such as anxiety, depression and self-criticism are the risk factors of compulsive buying. [7]

The shopping elicits in the subjects, a temporary reward sensation that provides relief from the negative stimuli but soon after he compulsive shopping, the short lived feeling of reward fades away and the temporary relief vanes, leading to a newfound and amplified sense of guilt, anxiety and stress. [8] In the long run, once a person becomes strongly addicted, acting on the impulse regularly drains a person's financial resources and forces him to encounter economic woes that otherwise would not have arisen in regular circumstances, leading to more

stress and depression like negative emotional stimuli. [9]

Compulsive behavior, however does not depend on just the few aforementioned factors, but on an amalgamation of several factors including social, genetic, cultural, physiological and psychological. While many of the previously defined factors that determine compulsive buying behavior have remained the same, it has been observed that compulsive buying behavior has risen considerably and so has its societal and economic impact. [10]

This research explores compulsive buying manifesting due to stress and ultimately leading to shopping addiction among working women i.e. the female teaching faculty at Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences, Mehran University of Engineering & Technology and University of Sindh that play host women hailing from diverse socioeconomic, cultural, religious and demographic backgrounds. Acute stress has been chosen, owing to the fact that we consider stress as the hypothetically strongest factor that induces compulsive buying.

METHODOLOGY:

This descriptive analysis was carried out from January 2017 to June 2017 upon a sample of 384 female employees (consenting faculty members of 3 major universities of Jamshoro, ranked BPS-18 and above) of Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences, University of Sindh and Mehran University of Engineering and Technology (MUET), chosen via non-probability, purposive sampling. Data was obtained via a self-structured, self-administered questionnaire and the Perceived Stress Scale after taking written informed consent. The data obtained was analyzed using SPSS v. 19.0 and Microsoft Excel.

Inclusion Criteria: Consenting female teaching faculty (BPS-18 and above) of Liaquat University of Medical & Health Sciences, Mehran University of Engineering and Technology and University of Sindh.

Exclusion Criteria: (1) Non-teaching female employees. (2) The female employees who were below BPS -18. (3) The female employees who were unwilling to participate in the study. (4) The female employees who did not belongs to LUMHS, MUET and University of Sindh.

RESULTS:

The mean age of the sample of 384 females, stood at 42 (± 13 SD). 81.25% of the respondents were

married, while the remaining 18.75% were un-married. 78.64% of the respondents hailed from an

urban setting and the rest of 21.36 respondents belonged to rural areas.

The respondents (BPS-18 and above) were designated either as lecturers (50%), assistant professors (26.5%), associate professors (14.6%) and professors (8.9%). The stress levels among the respondents were classified as low (26.56%), moderate (52.6%) and high (20.84%).

induced compulsive buying while the 18.75% did not partake in either of the two practices. 76.5% of the respondents had a self-realization that shopping addiction is an illness and merits treatment. 48% of all indulging in compulsive buying reportedly felt post-shopping regret. The probable (self-reported) causes of compulsive buying are as follows:

33.25% of the respondents were admittedly addicted to shopping, 48% admitted to indulging in stress

DISCUSSION:

Very few studies have been carried out in this region of the world regarding this very important public health concern. Compulsive buyers are faced with major personal and societal woes as a result of their compulsive habit. Researchers exploring the consumer market have long attempted to understand and describe the condition in clearer terms but struggle to do that till date. Thus with inadequate understanding and unclear guidelines of

management, the individuals faced with this condition are forced to suffer. [11] The habit of compulsive buying, when cemented by the passage of years becomes an individual’s primary coping mechanism to stress and other psychological distress such as frustration, disappointment and lack of self-esteem. Evidence based research has identified 3 primary aspects of compulsive buying. The first feature is the consumer’s irresistible desire to shop, the second is loss of control of the consumer over

his/her buying behavior and the final is the continuation of this behavior despite having witnessed the negative consequences. [12]

Literature also explains that once buying behavior is developed, the individual face great difficulty in controlling buying even after its detrimental effects are recognized. [13] Once an individual is unable to control buying, he will frequently purchase unnecessary items or more than what he can afford, and shop for longer periods than was planned. Research has shown that compulsive buying behavior is positively associated with stress-elimination tendencies and psychological distress coping behaviors. [14]

The compulsive buyers attempt to utilize the spending and shopping process hoping to eliminate stress, however, detailed interviews with research subjects revealed that they often end up just trading momentary stress for the feeling of shame, guilt or even procrastination although initially may work to stop the buyer from making un-needed future purchasing but the probability of that happening reduces every time the person gives in to the impulse, and concomitantly the feeling of shame and/or guilt too seem to vane away faster with every bout of indulgence in this behavior. [15] Family problems, marital discord, chronic anxiety and an impending financial failure may all result from this behavior. Thus it is very important that this important problem is not overlooked and gets more importance than just being lumped together with other minor impulse control disorders. In addition to that resources need to be allocated to devise strategies that may effectively counteract the materialistic mindset that preaches one to judge the self-worth by the amount of materialistic goods accumulated. [16]

CONCLUSION:

After careful consideration, it can be concluded that stress induced compulsive shopping among working women is common, resulting in most of the women developing an addiction towards shopping. The temporary relief from stress obtained from shopping is thus not an innocent pleasure but a sign of an impending trouble, thus it needs to be avoided and more healthy stress relief habits merit promotion. As the extent of this research was limited to female participants belonging to the working class, in future study should be carried out with added representative participants reflecting on broader demographical characteristics would put in added credibility to the findings.

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